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What is not possible is permitted

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Abstract:

Hintikka presented a controversial theorem. That theorem provided that, when something is impossible, that is not permitted. Although it is intuitively hard to accept, the theorem has received support. In particular, Prior proposed a system able to prove it. This paper tries to argue against Hintikka's theorem. For that, it only resorts to standard propositional logic, the operators of modal and deontic logic, and a conditional sentence that can be assumed as an axiom. In the argument, the theory of mental models also plays an important role.

Keywords: Hintikka's theorem; permission; possibility; prohibition; theory of mental models.

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Introduction

The theorem Hintikka proposed on possibility and permission is well known (see, e.g., Prior, 2012). The theorem expresses that if something is not possible, then that cannot be allowed. Its usual formal structure is the one in (1).

$$(1) \neg\Diamond p \rightarrow \neg Pp$$

In (1), ‘ \neg ’ denotes negation, ‘ \Diamond ’ is the modal operator of possibility, ‘ \rightarrow ’ stands for conditional relation, and ‘ P ’ is the deontic operator of permission.

A theorem of this kind is difficult to accept. It is counter-intuitive, since thinking about situations refuting it is easy. One of those situations can be that indicated in (2).

$$(2) \text{“...it is not possible to be 500 years old, but that is not forbidden” (López-Astorga, 2017, p. 63).}$$

Given that, in deontic logic, what is not forbidden is permitted (this idea is also developed below), (2) is a refutation for (1). The conditional is false when its antecedent is true and its consequent is not. In the case of (1), that means that it is false when something is not possible and is permitted. Because what is not forbidden is permitted, (2) refers to an instance of something that is not possible and is permitted at once (López-Astorga, 2017).

However, Prior (2012) offered a system demonstrating Hintikka’s theorem (see also Øhrstrøm, Zeller, & Sandborg-Petersen, 2012). So, if one does not want to accept (1), counterexamples such as (2) do not seem to be enough. It appears to be necessary to propose more logical and theoretical arguments. That is the main aim of this paper. It will present an argumentation of that type resorting just to the machinery of classical propositional logic, the usual operators in modal and deontic logic, and a conditional sentence that can be taken as an axiom. This last point is because, as it will be indicated, to assume that conditional can be reasonable and a common-sense action.

Thereby, to present the argumentation, the first section will delve into counterexamples such as (2) and its psychological relevance. The second one will address the common-sense conditional, its provenance, and the reasons to accept it. The final section will deal with the incompatibility between that conditional and (1).

Hintikka's theorem and the theory of mental models

Actually, (2) is an instance based on the theory of mental models (e.g., Byrne & Johnson-Laird, 2020). This theory is a psychological framework that, among other theses, claims that people process sentences by considering the combinations of possibilities or models corresponding to them (see also, e.g., Johnson-Laird & Ragni, 2019). This is easy to see from (3), which is (1) written in natural language.

(3) If p is not possible, then p is not allowed.

There are two important concepts in (3): possibility and permission. From those two concepts, four combinations or models can be deployed: (4), (5), (6), and (7) (see López-Astorga, 2017).

(4) p is possible and p is allowed

(5) p is possible and p is not allowed

(6) p is not possible and p is allowed

(7) p is not possible and p is not allowed

(Although expressed in other way, (4), (5), (6), and (7) are equivalent to [IV], [V], [VI], and [VII] in López-Astorga, 2017).

Both in classical logic and, in principle, in the theory of mental models, a conditional such as (1) admits (4), (5), and (7) as possible scenarios in which (1) is true (for the manner the theory of mental models initially deems the conditional and its combinations or models, see also, e.g., Khemlani, Byrne, & Johnson-Laird, 2018). Nevertheless, (6), that is, the case that makes (1) false, is, as pointed out, possible. (2) is an example in this regard.

One might think that this suffices to reject (1). After all, the theory of mental models is, as said, a psychological approach (see also, e.g., Khemlani & Johnson-Laird, 2019). Hence, the explanation in the previous paragraph can account for the reasons why people tend to reject (1) (López-Astorga, 2017). Nonetheless, perhaps something else is necessary. As mentioned, (2) is just a counterexample. Thus, although there is no doubt that more counterexamples such as (2) could be found, they could only offer factual evidence. Those counterexamples could only make (1), following Carnap (1947), F-false, that is, false because facts show that in a particular state-description or possible world. Given that Prior (2012) presented a system proving (1), maybe what is required is an argument revealing that, keeping following Carnap (1947), (1) is L-false, that is, false in all the state-descriptions or possible worlds because the language prevents it from being true.

However, this would be too strong: it would imply that (6) is the case in every state-description or possible world, which is hard to assume. What can be made is to offer an argument showing that (7) is possible in no state-description or possible world. That argument would reveal that a conditional such as (3) but with its consequent affirmed (and not negated) is true in all the state-descriptions or possible worlds. In other words, it would reveal that the only possible circumstances are (4), (5), and (6). The rest of the paper will try to find an argument of that type.

Combinations or models for prohibition and possibility

There are two concepts related to this issue that can be considered by virtue of linguistic criteria, and not just of empirical or factual criteria. In this way, it is possible to provide links between them, those links being analytic in the Kantian sense (Kant, 1998). The concepts are those of prohibition and possibility.

Resorting again to the methodological resources given by the theory of mental models, these four combinations can be established between those two concepts:

(8) p is forbidden and p is possible

(9) p is forbidden and p is not possible

- (10) p is not forbidden and p is possible
- (11) p is not forbidden and p is not possible

The only unacceptable combination of the set consisting of (8) to (11) is (9). No justice system, no law, and no rule are created to ban something impossible. If something is impossible, it will never be done. Therefore, although its consequences are very undesirable, it would be absurd to prohibit an action that can happen in no way. In fact, to provide bans in this direction could be deemed even as wasting time.

But, if this is correct, a conditional can be extracted from the remaining combinations, that is, from (8), (10), and (11). The proponents of the theory of mental models tend to state that the theory is not related to logic. In their view, hence, syntactic structures should not be derived from sets such as that including (8) to (11) (e.g., Johnson-Laird, 2010). The reason is that the models have an iconic nature (see also, e.g., Johnson-Laird, 2012) and the sets capture combinations of possibilities, and not truth tables (see also, e.g., Johnson-Laird & Ragni, 2019). However, studies inferring logical forms from sets of models such as the one with combinations (8) to (11) are to be found in the literature (e.g., López-Astorga, 2020). Thereby, taking both those works and the material interpretation of the conditional into account, (12) can be drawn from set (8) to (11). The reason is that, while, as said, (9) is impossible, (8), (10), and (11) are possible.

- (12) If p is forbidden, then p is possible.

And an important point about (12) is that it is L-true in the manner Carnap (1947) uses this expression, and, accordingly, analytic in the Kantian sense. This is because, given the relations between the concepts of prohibition and possibility indicated in this section, it is hard to imagine a state-description or possible world in which (12) is false. The words in it, and, therefore, language, seem to make that impossible.

The relation between impossibility and permission

Hence, it seems that it is reasonable to assume (12). It is a common-sense statement. So, it could be deemed as an axiom. Its formal expression would be (13).

$$(13) \quad PHp \rightarrow \diamond p$$

In (13), 'PH' is the deontic operator of prohibition.

By contraposition, (13) can be transformed into (14).

$$(14) \quad \neg \diamond p \rightarrow \neg PHp$$

However, as it is well known, (15) usually holds in deontic logic.

$$(15) \quad \neg PHp \leftrightarrow Pp$$

Where ' \leftrightarrow ' stands for logical equivalence.

Therefore, (14) is equivalent to (16).

$$(16) \quad \neg \diamond p \rightarrow Pp$$

This makes it hard to accept (1); (16) implies the opposite of (1). Accordingly, all of this can be considered as evidence in favor of the rejection of (1). The only elements that have been needed have been classical propositional logic, the habitual modal and deontic operators, and (13), which has been taken as an axiom.

Of course, one might argue that the same could be done from set including (4) to (7). These last combinations also show that (1) is not correct, since, as explained, (2) is a case of (6). In addition, as claimed for (9), it can be said that (7) is hard to admit as well. It is difficult to think about something impossible that has been explicitly labelled as not permitted. If an action is not possible, from the legal or ethical point of view, it is not relevant. It refers to a situation that will happen in no state-description or possible world. Therefore, no deontic judgment should be issued for it.

But, if this is the case, it has to be accepted that (4), (5), and (6) are possible and that (7) is not. So, in the same way as (12) has been derived from set (8) to (11), (17) can be deduced from set (4) to (7).

(17) If p is not possible, then p is permitted.

The logical form of (17) is (16). Hence, this can be a shorter route to come to the same result, that is, to the rejection of (1).

However, perhaps the derivation of (12) from set (8) to (11) is preferable. The one following set (4) to (7) and coming to (17) is not very different from the account that has been presented in the literature to explain the psychological reasons why people reject (1) (López-Astorga, 2017). According to this last account, individuals focus on the models related to the concepts present in (1) (i.e., the concepts of possibility and permission). As indicated, those models are (4) to (7). They note that one of those combinations -(6)- makes (1) false, and that, in fact, that very combination can happen. Thereby, what the present paper adds is that, from that datum and the facts that (4) and (5) can also occur and that (7) is inadmissible, (17) -or (16)- can be recovered. Besides, (17) -or (16)- can be deemed as a L-true sentence, since, as pointed out, it is hard to find a state description or possible world in which (7) is the case.

In the case of (12) and combinations (8) to (11), the deduction can be considered even stronger because it draws from a different concept. That concept is important in deontic logic and is not explicitly included in (1). It is the one of prohibition. The combinations considering this concept and that of possibility, that is, models (8) to (11) lead to a L-true conditional too, that is, (12). Nevertheless, the interesting point in this derivation is that, by virtue of purely logical transformations, namely, transformations from (13) to (14) and from (14) to (16), it is possible to come to the same conditional hard to accept with (1) at once: (16). This means that, in addition to the direct rejection provided by the deduction of (16) from set (4) to (7), a sequence of logical inference coming to (16) can also be proposed. That sequence starts with (13), which can be assumed as an axiom, and comes to (16) because of the logical

transformations indicated. Therefore, because (16) can be obtained following different paths, the reasons to reject (1) are not just one.

Conclusions

Indeed, there are at a minimum two reasons to think that (1) does not hold. On the one hand, to accept it seems difficult for common sense. This is, at least, if the theory of mental models is right about its idea that individuals make analysis of combinations or models (López-Astorga, 2017). Furthermore, taking methods used in the literature into account (López-Astorga, 2020), it is also possible to draw a conditional –(16)- from the models corresponding to the concepts included in (1) which is difficult to accept with (1) at the same time.

On the other hand, a conditional working as an axiom can be admitted from other deontic concept as well: the concept of prohibition. The combinations related to this last concept and the one of possibility allow deriving a conditional –(13)- too. This last conditional is logically equivalent to (16), that is, to the one obtained by considering just the concepts used in (1).

Accordingly, it can be said that there are psychological, logical, and linguistic criteria to reject (1). However, all of this also leads to other conclusions linked to the discussion on the possible relations between logic and the human mind.

First, as indicated, the proponents of the theory of mental models generally tend not to accept relations between logic and the intellectual human activity. Nevertheless, the arguments above appear to reveal that the theory of mental models can offer a method to identify the logical systems that are coherent with the way the human mind works. Thereby, the interesting systems would be those compatible with models that people assume in sets such as that of (4) to (7) and that of (8) to (11). This is because those systems would be consistent with the real manner individuals think. From this perspective, systems such as the one of Prior (2012), being logically correct, would move away from the real processes occurring when people reason.

Second, what has been argued here has an effect on the theory of mental models too. Confirming theses already presented in the literature (e.g., López-Astorga, 2020), it can be claimed that not only it is possible to find connections between logic and the theory of mental models. Those connections can complement the theory and be very useful to study the real characteristics of human thought. So, it is evident that proposals such as the one of the present paper show the possible benefits of analyzing theorems such as (1) from the approach of the theory of mental models.

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